

1 **ALK, independent of rearrangement status, is a therapeutic target in metastasis to the brain in lung**
2 **cancer.**

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7 The anaplastic lymphoma kinase ALK is a driver of the brain cancer neuroblastoma (1, 2) and rearrangements
8 of ALK (EML4-ALK) are found in a small percentage of patients with lung cancer (3-6). A significant fraction
9 of humans with lung cancer will develop metastasis to the central nervous system (CNS), where the primary
10 tumor spreads to the brain or other CNS organs including the spine. We performed expression screening by
11 comparing total transcription in primary tumors and metastases to the brain in humans with lung cancer to
12 identify by quantitative methods kinases that promote survival of tumor in the CNS (7). We identified the ALK
13 as a candidate therapeutic target in CNS metastatic lung cancer. ALK was differentially expressed and
14 up-regulated in CNS metastatic lung cancer. First-progression survival was 40 months in patients with low
15 tumor expression of ALK, but 164 months in patients with high tumor expression of ALK. Pharmacologic
16 inhibition of ALK is a novel therapeutic approach for management of CNS metastatic disease in humans with
17 lung cancer.
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